

FEATURE OF LINGUISTIC MISTAKES IN CONSECUTIVE INTERPRETATION AND THE WAYS TO OVERCOME THEM

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Abstract: Consecutive interpretation, a key practice in cross-linguistic communication, often encounters various linguistic mistakes that impact the effectiveness of interpretation. This article examines the features of these mistakes, their underlying causes, and strategies for overcoming them, referencing works by scholars from Uzbekistan and abroad. A focus is placed on the importance of training, note-taking skills, and stress management in reducing errors.

Keywords: consecutive interpretation, linguistic mistakes, ways of overcoming mistakes.

Аннотация: Последовательный перевод, являясь важной практикой в межкультурной коммуникации, часто сопровождается различными лингвистическими ошибками, которые влияют на эффективность перевода. В статье рассматриваются особенности этих ошибок, их причины и стратегии их преодоления с опорой на работы ученых Узбекистана и зарубежья. Особое внимание уделено важности подготовки, навыков конспектирования и управления стрессом для снижения ошибок.

Ключевые слова: последовательный перевод, лингвистические ошибки, преодоление ошибок.

Annotatsiya: Ketma-ket tarjima, tillararo muloqotning muhim qismi sifatida, ko‘pincha xatolar bilan bog‘liq bo‘ladi, bu esa tarjimaning samaradorligiga ta‘sir qiladi. Ushbu maqola ushbu xatolar xususiyatlari, ularning sabablari va ularni bartaraf etish usullarini o‘rganadi. O‘zbekiston va xorijiy olimlarning ilmiy ishlari asosida tahlil olib boriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: ketma-ket tarjima, lingvistik hatolar, hatolarni to‘g‘irlash.

INTRODUCTION

Consecutive interpretation is a dynamic and challenging practice that demands a high degree of cognitive flexibility, linguistic proficiency, and cultural sensitivity. Unlike simultaneous interpretation, where interpreters deliver translations in real-time alongside the speaker, consecutive interpretation involves listening to a segment of speech, analyzing its meaning, and then rendering it into the target language after the speaker pauses. This process places significant demands on the interpreter’s working

memory, note-taking skills, and ability to navigate linguistic and cultural complexities.

Errors in consecutive interpretation are inevitable due to the intricacy of the task. These mistakes can occur at multiple linguistic levels, including lexical (word choice), syntactic (sentence structure), and semantic (meaning) domains. Lexical errors often stem from insufficient vocabulary or misunderstanding of domain-specific terminology. Syntactic errors arise when interpreters struggle to align the grammatical structures of the source and target languages, while semantic errors typically result from misinterpretation of the speaker's intent or cultural nuances. Such errors can lead to significant distortions in communication, affecting the credibility of the interpreter and the outcome of the interpreted interaction.

The causes of these errors are multifaceted, involving both internal and external factors. Internally, interpreters must grapple with cognitive load, as they simultaneously listen, analyze, and plan their output. Externally, they face challenges such as linguistic disparities, cultural differences, and the pressure of maintaining accuracy under time constraints. Scholars like Gile have emphasized the importance of understanding these challenges to develop effective training methods.⁴³ Similarly, Djurayev⁴⁴ and Abduvaliyeva⁴⁵ have explored strategies to address these difficulties, including targeted skill development and the implementation of cognitive aids like structured note-taking.

This article aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the features of linguistic mistakes in consecutive interpretation and their underlying causes. Drawing on seminal works such as those by Gile, Abduvaliyeva, and Djurayeva, it also outlines practical strategies to overcome these challenges. By synthesizing insights from Uzbek and international scholars, this discussion seeks to contribute to the ongoing efforts to enhance the quality and reliability of consecutive interpretation in diverse contexts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Features of Linguistic Mistakes in Consecutive Interpretation.

1. Lexical Errors

Lexical errors, one of the most common types of linguistic mistakes in consecutive interpretation, occur when interpreters choose incorrect words or phrases to convey the intended meaning of the source text. These mistakes are often linked to a limited vocabulary, particularly in specialized or technical domains, where the interpreter might lack familiarity with specific terms. Abduvaliyeva notes that

⁴³ Gile, D. (2009). *Basic Concepts and Models for Interpreter and Translator Training* (Revised Edition). Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing. – P.105

⁴⁴ Djurayeva, M. A. Q. (2023). *Developing Note-Taking Skills in Consecutive Interpreting*. Chirchik: Chirchik State Pedagogical University. – P.232-233.

⁴⁵ Abduvaliyeva, M. (2023). *The Concept of Interpretation and Common Mistakes in Consecutive Interpretation*. Tashkent: Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature.

interpreters frequently encounter challenges when dealing with domain-specific terminology, such as legal, medical, or technical jargon.⁴⁶ Misuse of terminology not only distorts the message but can also undermine the credibility of the interpreter. Additionally, confusion between similar-sounding words or terms with overlapping meanings in the source and target languages further contributes to lexical errors. For instance, terms that carry multiple meanings depending on context can be particularly problematic, as the interpreter must quickly discern the correct usage based on the surrounding discourse.

2. Syntactic Errors

Syntactic errors arise when interpreters fail to maintain the grammatical structure of the source language in their translation into the target language. These mistakes often stem from significant structural differences between the two languages, such as word order, verb placement, or the use of modifiers. Gile emphasizes that syntactic mismatches are particularly prevalent in language pairs with markedly different grammar systems, such as English and Uzbek.⁴⁷ For instance, English follows a Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) structure, whereas Uzbek often uses a Subject-Object-Verb (SOV) structure. When interpreters attempt to retain the syntactic form of the source language without adapting it to the grammar rules of the target language, the result is often a confusing or ungrammatical sentence. These errors may also occur when interpreters prioritize speed over grammatical accuracy, especially under the pressure of retaining the speaker's meaning while managing cognitive load.

3. Semantic and Conceptual Errors

Semantic and conceptual errors are among the most serious mistakes in consecutive interpretation, as they directly affect the meaning and intent of the original message. These errors occur when interpreters fail to grasp the context or cultural nuances of the source language. According to **González, R. D., Vásquez, V. F., & Mikkelson, H.**, cultural competence is a critical skill for interpreters, as it helps them navigate idiomatic expressions, metaphors, and culturally specific references that may not have direct equivalents in the target language.⁴⁸ For example, an interpreter might misunderstand an idiomatic expression in English, such as "break the ice," and render it literally in Uzbek, resulting in a loss of meaning. Conceptual errors can also occur when interpreters misinterpret the speaker's intent, either due to a lack of context or insufficient preparation for the subject matter. These mistakes not

⁴⁶ **Abduvaliyeva, M.** (2023). The Concept of Interpretation and Common Mistakes in Consecutive Interpretation. Tashkent: Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature. – P.90

⁴⁷ **Gile, D.** (2009). Basic Concepts and Models for Interpreter and Translator Training (Revised Edition). Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing. – P.142

⁴⁸ **González, R. D., Vásquez, V. F., & Mikkelson, H.** (2012). Fundamentals of Court Interpretation: Theory, Policy, and Practice (2nd ed.). Durham, NC: Carolina Academic Press. – P. 92.

only compromise the accuracy of the interpretation but can also lead to significant misunderstandings in professional or diplomatic settings.

4. Note-Taking Challenges

Effective note-taking is a cornerstone of successful consecutive interpretation, as it helps interpreters retain key information during longer speeches or segments of discourse. However, note-taking itself can be a source of errors if it is poorly executed. Djurayeva emphasizes that interpreters with underdeveloped note-taking skills often struggle to recall details accurately, leading to omissions, distortions, or a reliance on memory that might not capture the nuances of the original message.⁴⁹ Common challenges include a lack of standardized symbols or abbreviations, disorganized notes, or an inability to balance note-taking with active listening. Additionally, interpreters who over-rely on writing down verbatim phrases may find it difficult to restructure and adapt the message to the target language, further increasing the likelihood of syntactic and lexical errors. Training in systematic note-taking, including the use of visual aids and prioritization of key ideas, can significantly reduce these issues and improve overall interpretation quality.

Causes of Errors in Consecutive Interpretation

1. Cognitive Load

The process of consecutive interpretation involves managing multiple cognitive tasks simultaneously, including listening to the source message, analyzing its meaning, storing information in memory, and rendering the message into the target language. Gile's Effort Models emphasize that these activities compete for the interpreter's limited cognitive resources, often leading to errors when the cognitive load exceeds the interpreter's capacity.⁵⁰ This is particularly evident during long speeches or when dealing with complex subject matter, where interpreters may struggle to retain and accurately recall all details. The multitasking nature of interpretation creates a high potential for omissions, inaccuracies, or incomplete renditions, especially if the interpreter's working memory becomes overloaded. Factors such as the speed of the speaker's delivery, the density of information, and unfamiliar terminology can further exacerbate the cognitive strain, making it challenging to maintain both accuracy and fluency.

2. Anxiety and Stress

The high-pressure environment of consecutive interpretation often induces significant levels of anxiety and stress, which can impair cognitive performance and increase the likelihood of errors. As noted by Russell, stress affects the interpreter's ability to concentrate, process information efficiently, and make quick decisions

⁴⁹ Djurayeva, M. A. Q. (2023). Developing Note-Taking Skills in Consecutive Interpreting. Chirchik: Chirchik State Pedagogical University. – P.232-233.

⁵⁰ Gile, D. (2009). Basic Concepts and Models for Interpreter and Translator Training (Revised Edition). Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing. – P.150

about word choice and sentence structure. Anxiety may lead to hesitation, disrupted fluency, and errors such as omissions or substitutions, particularly when interpreters are inexperienced or lack confidence.⁵¹ Additionally, stress can have a physiological impact, such as increased heart rate or difficulty breathing, which may further hinder performance. Situations with high stakes—such as legal or medical interpretations—can amplify these stress levels, making it even more critical for interpreters to develop coping mechanisms. Regular practice, preparation, and stress management techniques, such as mindfulness or relaxation exercises, are essential for reducing anxiety and maintaining performance under pressure.

3. *Language Proficiency*

A strong command of both the source and target languages is foundational to successful consecutive interpretation. Limited proficiency in either language can lead to misinterpretations, incorrect word choices, or an inability to convey nuanced meanings. Angelelli highlights that interpreters with insufficient language skills may struggle with complex syntax, idiomatic expressions, or culturally specific terminology, which can result in distortions or omissions of the message. Language proficiency also includes a deep understanding of the context in which specific phrases or terms are used.⁵² For instance, interpreters who lack familiarity with the specialized language of fields such as law, medicine, or technology may find it challenging to deliver accurate and precise interpretations. Continuous language development, including exposure to diverse registers and terminologies, is essential for interpreters to perform effectively across different domains.

4. *Cultural Barriers*

Cultural differences between the source and target languages present a significant challenge in consecutive interpretation. **Gentile, A., Ozolins, U., & Vasilakakos, M.** highlight that interpreters must not only translate linguistic content but also navigate the cultural nuances embedded in the message. This includes idiomatic expressions, metaphors, humor, and references to cultural practices or historical events that may not have direct equivalents in the target language.⁵³ Misinterpretation of these elements can result in errors that distort the intended meaning or fail to convey the speaker's message effectively. For example, an idiom like "it's raining cats and dogs" in English would be confusing if rendered literally into another language. Cultural competence, therefore, is a crucial skill for interpreters, requiring them to not only understand cultural references but also adapt them appropriately to ensure the message remains meaningful in the target culture.

⁵¹ **Russell, D.** (2004). Consecutive and Simultaneous Interpreting. In E. M. Varela (Ed.), *Studies in Interpretation* (pp. 135-150). Washington, D.C.: Gallaudet University Press. – P.135-150

⁵² **Angelelli, C. V.** (2004). Revisiting the Interpreter's Role: A Study of Conference, Court, and Medical Interpreters in Canada, Mexico, and the United States. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing. – P. 79.

⁵³ **Gentile, A., Ozolins, U., & Vasilakakos, M.** (1996). *Liaison Interpreting: A Handbook*. Carlton South, Vic., Australia: Melbourne University Press. – P. 50.

This can be achieved through cultural immersion, specialized training, and ongoing study of the cultural contexts of both languages.

RESULTS

1. *Comprehensive Training Programs*

Effective training programs are the foundation for minimizing linguistic mistakes in consecutive interpretation. These programs should encompass a combination of language development, domain-specific knowledge, and practical interpreting techniques. According to Abduvaliyeva, interpreters benefit most from training that integrates real-world scenarios, allowing them to practice handling complex and varied content. Training should also focus on enhancing interpreters' ability to manage cognitive load, through activities designed to improve memory retention, multitasking, and quick decision-making.⁵⁴ Additionally, specialized training modules targeting specific fields, such as legal or medical interpretation, can help interpreters become familiar with the terminology and unique challenges of these domains. Regular feedback from experienced mentors is essential in guiding trainees to refine their skills and address recurring errors, ensuring a gradual progression toward professional competency.

2. *Enhanced Note-Taking Skills*

Note-taking is a critical skill in consecutive interpretation, serving as a cognitive aid to capture key information during the listening phase. However, effective note-taking requires a systematic approach that balances the need for detail with the constraints of time and clarity. Djurayeva highlights the importance of developing a personalized note-taking system, including the use of symbols, abbreviations, and structured layouts to organize information. Training in note-taking should emphasize prioritizing main ideas, avoiding over-reliance on verbatim transcription, and learning to quickly reconstruct meaning from notes. Techniques such as column-based structures for separating main ideas and details, as well as visual aids like diagrams or arrows to indicate relationships between concepts, can further enhance the utility of notes. Consistent practice in real-time scenarios is crucial for interpreters to internalize these techniques and adapt them to their individual needs.⁵⁵

3. *Stress Management Techniques*

Stress is a major factor that impairs interpreters' performance, making the development of effective stress management strategies essential. Russell advocates for the use of mindfulness practices, such as deep breathing exercises, progressive muscle relaxation, and visualization techniques, to help interpreters maintain focus

⁵⁴ **Abduvaliyeva, M.** (2023). The Concept of Interpretation and Common Mistakes in Consecutive Interpretation. Tashkent: Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature.

⁵⁵ **Djurayeva, M. A. Q.** (2023). Developing Note-Taking Skills in Consecutive Interpreting. Chirchik: Chirchik State Pedagogical University. – P.232-233.

and calm under pressure.⁵⁶ Preparing interpreters to anticipate and cope with high-stakes situations can reduce performance anxiety and enable them to concentrate on the task at hand. Training programs should incorporate stress management as a core component, equipping interpreters with tools to handle both anticipated and unexpected challenges. Additionally, creating a supportive work environment, where interpreters feel valued and encouraged, can significantly alleviate stress. Building resilience through regular self-care practices and maintaining a balanced workload further ensures that interpreters can perform at their best even in demanding circumstances.

4. Pre-Assignment Preparation

Preparation is a vital step in ensuring the quality and accuracy of consecutive interpretation. Gillies emphasizes that interpreters who invest time in researching the subject matter, terminology, and cultural context of an assignment are better equipped to handle its linguistic and conceptual demands. Pre-assignment preparation should include reviewing relevant documents, such as glossaries, speeches, or background information, and familiarizing oneself with the context of the discourse.⁵⁷ Interpreters should also anticipate potential challenges, such as technical jargon, idiomatic expressions, or culturally specific references, and prepare strategies to address them. Collaborative preparation with clients or event organizers can provide additional insights into the expected content and help establish clear communication about expectations. By dedicating time to thorough preparation, interpreters can significantly reduce the risk of errors and enhance their confidence in delivering accurate and meaningful interpretations.

DISCUSSION

Consecutive interpretation, as a demanding and multifaceted process, is inherently prone to a variety of linguistic mistakes. These errors are shaped by a complex interplay of cognitive limitations, linguistic proficiency, and cultural factors. Challenges such as cognitive overload, anxiety, insufficient language skills, and cultural misunderstandings can compromise the quality of interpretation, leading to inaccuracies that may distort the intended message. However, with the implementation of targeted strategies and a focus on skill development, many of these errors can be effectively mitigated.

Comprehensive training programs that emphasize language proficiency, cognitive management, and domain-specific knowledge are pivotal in preparing interpreters for the complexities of their profession. Enhancing note-taking skills and adopting systematic approaches to organizing information can significantly improve

⁵⁶ **Russell, D.** (2004). Consecutive and Simultaneous Interpreting. In E. M. Varela (Ed.), *Studies in Interpretation* (pp. 135-150). Washington, D.C.: Gallaudet University Press. – P. 135-150.

⁵⁷ **Gillies, Andrew.** *Consecutive Interpreting: A Short Course*. London: Routledge, 2019. – P.43

memory retention and reduce omissions or distortions. Additionally, equipping interpreters with stress management techniques ensures they are better able to perform under pressure, maintaining accuracy and composure in high-stakes situations. Pre-assignment preparation, including in-depth research on terminology and cultural context, further empowers interpreters to deliver precise and culturally sensitive interpretations.

As the field of interpretation continues to evolve, particularly with the increasing demands of globalized communication, there is a pressing need for ongoing research and innovation. Advances in cognitive science, language studies, and technology offer opportunities to refine training methodologies and develop new tools to support interpreters. Collaborative efforts between academic researchers, professional interpreters, and training institutions are essential to address emerging challenges and ensure the highest standards of interpretation practice.

In conclusion, while consecutive interpretation is inherently challenging, a proactive approach to skill development and professional preparation can enable interpreters to overcome its associated linguistic and cognitive obstacles. By fostering a deeper understanding of the factors influencing errors and implementing evidence-based solutions, the field can continue to advance, contributing to more effective and accurate cross-cultural communication in an increasingly interconnected world.

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